

Responsibilities Implemented by School Administrators for Enhancing Students' Discipline in Secondary Schools: A Case of Itilima District-Tanzania

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KEYWORDS: Students discipline, school administrators, professional development, guest speaker, behaviour support programme.

ABSTRACT: The study aimed to investigate various responsibilities which are implemented by school administrators in school environment for enhancing students' discipline in Itilima secondary schools. The theory X and theory Y was used to guide the study. The study adopted convergent design that is under mixed method research approach. The sample size was 75 from 516 total population including heads of schools and teachers. The respondents were obtained through purposive sampling and total population sampling. The data collection tools were interview guides and questionnaires. Techniques for data analysis were thematic and descriptive statistics. The findings reveal that school administrators in school environment implement various responsibilities including; Invitation of guest speaker, time management, establishment of clear policies, consistence enforcement of rules, positive behaviour support program, professional development for staff, monitoring students' behaviour as well as engagement with parents and community. The study concludes that the responsibilities which are implemented by school administrators are effective for shaping students' discipline as a result of decreasing in number of students with negative behaviour decrease in school environment. The study recommends that teachers to be innovative in coming with new ways of shaping students' discipline which do not affect student psychologically. Students should follow the guidelines which are communicated by teachers and other school administrators to them for enhancing their academic and social progress.

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INTRODUCTION

The word "Discipline" means following societal rules and regulations. On the other hand, indiscipline involves disobedience to the norms and values which are governing a certain society. In school environment, discipline enables students to comply with school rules and principles for enhancing their holistic development. In America, there are common indiscipline behaviours among students including; high truancy rates, vandalism, theft on school properties, disrespecting the staff members, and extortion. Students with good discipline are seen to have good academic achievement and reduce unnecessary conflicts which are caused by indiscipline issues. (Taylor Bunce et al., 2022).

In Mauritius, students' behaviours are driven by different factors including; Peer influence, family background, social cultural changes, school environment as well as science and technological development. Strategies such as equipping students with social-emotional skills are done to enable them in improving their social competence reducing their disruptive behaviours in school environment and their living community (Belle, 2017). Moreover, in Cameroon, teachers and the school management team have responsibilities of providing instructions to students concerning the moral education, enforcing the discipline rules and regulations together with the implementation of moral leadership. Those trainings which are being provided are directed to solve the indiscipline issues such as disobedience, students' collective misconducts and inappropriate behaviours which are caused by students, school management and absence of resources in secondary schools (Ngwokabueni, 2015).

In Kenya, inadequate of management skills and abilities among educational institution leaders results to outbreak of indiscipline issues in school environment (Kubai et al., 2017). The rules and regulations are not clearly which lead to lack of belief among students on the rules, conflicts among teachers and administrators regarding the established rules as well as poor cooperation between teachers and administrators in solving the indiscipline issues (Mirit, 2017).

In Tanzania, Indiscipline issues remain as a pivotal challenge among public secondary schools. Students engage in inappropriate behaviours due to several reasons such as poor attitudes towards education, poor parental cooperation in managing students' discipline, ineffective among staff members in enforcing rules and regulations which can strengthen students' discipline (Aymelo, 2022). Apart from teaching activities, teachers have responsibilities of supporting students' discipline. In now days teachers use a lot of time in managing students' behaviours compared to supervision of teaching and learning responsibilities due to high volume of indiscipline cases among students in secondary schools (Kambuga, 2017). Moreover, students' misbehaviours are caused by adopting the inappropriate actions from their surroundings including; Alcoholism, cigarette smoking, drug abuse and observations of inappropriate action in television and cell phones (Kiwale, 2017).

In addition, the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology Education published the Education Act No. 25 of 1978 (as amended by Act No. 10 of 1995) for providing guidelines to school administrators for making decision concerning discipline issues in schools. school administrators are encouraged to use the suitable policies and procedures for maintaining efficiency in school operations (Yakubjonov, 2021).

Normally, the head of school guide book provides details on job description such as to ensure school calendar includes time for regular meetings, where both teachers and parents can be involved in discussing students' disciplinary matters and employing appropriate administrative strategies to promote student discipline (Otaru & Uwanyirigira, 2018). In spite of the identified roles, the indiscipline cases including burning of schools, use of abusive language, truancy, fighting, drug abuse, stealing, and alcoholism are common among students in Itilima district. Students' indiscipline is a concern for education administrators, teachers, parents, and other education stakeholders. Heads of schools and teachers are blamed for students' indiscipline in secondary schools (Musa & Martha, 2020).

If indiscipline' issues couldn't be solved in secondary schools. Some problems such as dropouts, deviant behaviours, lateness, and poor academic performance among students will be dominant in secondary schools. Little attention has been paid to the strategies used by the heads of schools, even though heads of schools are identified as playing a crucial role in shaping students' discipline (Duda & Susilo, 2018; Maingi et al., 2017). To address this gap, the researcher explored how school administration contributes to enhancing student discipline in public secondary schools in the district.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Theory Used in the Study

The study was guided by the theory X and theory Y which was developed by Douglas McGregor's in 1960. McGregor grouped people into two categories including those who are supposed to be handled by theory X and theory Y. the theory X perceive individuals as lazy and ignore responsibilities. For them to adopt their responsibilities, they must be supervised closely, controlled, threatened and coerced. Concerning the theory Y, individuals are viewed as disciplined and they can adopt their responsibilities willingly without force and coercions (McGregor, 1960). Therefore, the study is related to theory X and theory Y because even students can be categorized into two groups, those who can be controlled through theory X by using coercion and punishment to manage their discipline. Schools that will use theory X, students will be controlled and directed and even threatened especially when breaking school rules and regulations. Also, others can be controlled using theory Y by communicating to them rules and regulations which can be followed as well as creating conducive environment which will influence them to practice acceptable conducts in schools. Schools that will use theory Y, students will be treated with respect and especially when they will behave inappropriately; they will patiently be taught and encouraged.

Responsibilities of School Administrators in Maintaining Students Discipline

The function of school administration in upholding student discipline, engaging with the wider community, which includes parents, neighbourhood organizations, and legislators, is encouraged for educational leaders. School leaders can boost student support, secure school resources, and promote policies that benefit the entire educational community by establishing solid partnerships and communication channels. Fundamentally, educational leadership theory emphasizes how school leaders can influence positive change, cultivate a culture of cooperation and ongoing development, and ultimately advance the academic achievement and general well-being of all students (Kunni, 2021).

Asare et al., (2015) conducted a study in Effutu Municipality to investigate how teachers in Effutu Municipality carry out their individual responsibilities in managing indiscipline and how students view this involvement. The study used a qualitative approach and a case study design. Thirty-six (36) respondents were purposefully chosen, consisting of twenty-four (24) students and twelve (12) teachers from two (2) public junior high schools. Interviews were used to collect data, which was then subjected to thematic analysis. The results showed that teachers serve a variety of functions, including judging subjective behaviours and assessing disciplinary actions to determine the best course of action to prevent misbehaviours. Teachers stopped demotivating their students

and began expressing verbal gratitude. They chose to support the students who were not participating in class activities rather than punish them. A peaceful teaching-learning environment is produced by considering students' misbehaviours and making sure the right steps are taken to prevent physical discomfort. The researcher had to use mixed method research approach which employ large sample compared qualitative research approach which involved two schools with only 36 respondents which were very few. To cover the gap the researcher employed mixed method research approach by involving 4 schools with 75 sample size. In addition, the researcher had to involve parents so as to notify how student behave in home environment because some time students tend to be had different at school and in home surrounding. Moreover, researchers had to include heads of schools for gaining more insight on how they play role in managing discipline.

Idris (2021) studied on the influence of head teachers discipline management on students' academic performance in public schools in Somalia. The study employed mixed research approach with a sample size of 307 respondents who were 8 teachers, 8 head teachers and 291 students. The researcher came up with the roles of head teachers in discipline management including time management, administration of school rules and regulation as well as punishment administration. Those played roles influenced students' academic performance. To critique, the researcher had to increase number of teachers who were to be selected as respondents because are the ones who interact with students and notes their behaviours. To cover such gap the researcher increased the number of teachers so as to get complete insights on the roles which are performed by teachers in school environment.

In Ntungamo Municipality, Uganda, Asimwe and Kamugisha (2024) conducted research on the function of guidance and counselling in fostering student discipline in secondary schools. Both qualitative and quantitative methods were used in a cross-sectional study design. Between March and May 2023, a sample of 40 students and 10 teachers from four randomly chosen schools took part in the study. In order to gauge their exposure to counselling and their opinions of how guidance affects behaviour, students filled out a questionnaire. Teachers participated in in-depth interviews to share their thoughts on counselling effects and disciplinary trends. The researchers demonstrated the functions of school administrators in upholding discipline in the classroom, such as allocating funds to the department, invite a special guest speaker. oversee all of the school's guidance and counselling services, provide comprehensive guidance and counselling services to the entire school community, formulate school policies that govern the guidance and counselling services in the school, provide resource materials required in the department for counselling and Provide guidance and counselling. To critique, the researcher had to include heads of schools in the study for the aim of seeking more information on how those roles are planned and implemented effectively, so in this study the researcher involved heads of schools.

Mpokera (2019) conducted research on how school administration oversees student behaviour. This study examined the extent to which improving student discipline in Tanzanian secondary schools is largely dependent on school administration. It was carried out in the Dodoma Region, specifically in the districts of Chamwino and Dodoma Urban. The study included 132 respondents in total. Qualitative content analysis was used to analyse the data gathered from focus groups, interviews, and documentary reviews. Through interviews, teachers, discipline masters or mistresses, and headmasters or headmistresses shared their perspectives on their roles as school administrators in overseeing student behaviour. In addition to communicating the school's rules and regulations to students, the head of school, second master or mistress, academic master or mistress, and discipline master or mistress must collaborate with one another and document instances of indiscipline in the black book. Make sure the teachers are available at the school.

METHODS

Research Approach and Design

The study employed a mixed method research approach which involves collection of both quantitative and qualitative data. Researchers have adopted the approach in order to get a complete understanding on the roles which are played by school administrators in managing students' discipline (Johnson & Christie, 2019). In addition, research design refers to the procedures and guidelines of conducting research. It provides a detailed description of information for sampling, data collection and analysis processes. In this study, researchers have employed the convergent design which merges both quantitative and qualitative data at equal weight in to obtain different perspective within a single phenomenon (Creswell & Creswell, 2018).

Area of Study, Population and Sample Size

The study was carried out in Itilima District Council which found in Simiyu Region. It involved four public secondary schools. The researcher chose to involve Itilima District Council due to the fact that no specific study on the same topic had been conducted in secondary schools and recently studies has reported on existence of indiscipline cases among students within Itilima District Council (Musa & Martha, 2020). According to Creswell and Creswell (2018), the term "population" refers to a collection of other living organisms like bacteria, grasshoppers, or mosquitoes. The target population included 516 people including 33 head of schools and 483 teachers composed of heads of schools and teachers from 33 secondary schools in the Itilima District Council. Sample size involves a total number of individuals who have been selected a representative of a certain population (Mugenyi & Mokoro, (2022). The researchers used a total number of 75 respondents including; 4 heads of schools and 71 teachers from four schools.

Sampling Techniques and Procedures

Sampling involves selection of representatives from a population (Hossan et al., 2023). Sampling is categorized into probability sampling which provide chance to each individual to be included in a sample and non-probability sampling which do not provide chance for everyone to be selected as representatives. The researchers used simple random sampling in selection of schools which were used in provision of data, total population sampling was used in selection of teachers where the researcher involved all teachers who were available in the sampled schools and expert purposive sampling was used to sample heads of schools who were identified as school administrators.

Data Collection Tools and Analysis Procedures

Data collection tools refer to instruments or equipment's which are used in gathering of data from the participants. They consist of checklists, telescopes, microscopes, satellite systems, observation schedules, and questionnaires (Cresswell & Cresswell, 2023). In this study, the researchers used questionnaires in collection of data from teachers which consisted of open-ended and closed-ended questions. Also, interview guides were used to collect data from heads of school. The obtained data were analysed through thematically by using the scheme of codes which categorized themes and subthemes. On the other hand, quantitative data were analysed descriptively by using the SPSS (version 23) which provided results in form of percentages and means which were presented in tables.

Validity and Reliability of Research Instruments

Creswell and Creswell (2018) the degree to which an instrument accurately measures what it is supposed to measure is known as validity. For confirmation of research instruments on the aspect of validity, the research tools were reviewed by expertise and areas of improvement were suggested and corrected. Moreover, the results which were provided by participants in a pilot study were related to the research problem. On the other hand, Reliability is the ability of measuring instrument to give similar results when applied at different times (Surucu & Maslakci 2020). For the purpose of ensuring reliability, the constructed tools were given to 16 respondents to fill out and analysed using the SPSS programme where the Cronbach alpha was 0.723 signifying that the tool was good and acceptable. This led the researcher to precede with data collection processes from the field.

Research Ethics

Researcher ethics refers to guidelines and principles which govern researchers when conducting research studies. These principles help to avoid harm to the research participants in term of physical and emotional. Also, they add credibility of the research study (Creswell & Creswell, 2018). In this study, Researchers adhered to ethical principles such as ensuring participants confidentiality, transparency, honesty, and obtaining the informed consents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Researchers conducted an investigation on the responsibilities which were implemented by the school administrators in enhancing students' discipline in secondary schools. Data were collected through questionnaire, interview guide and documentary analysis.

Table 1: Tools Return rate

Research tool	Sampled respondents	Return rate in F (%)
Questionnaires for teachers	71	71(100%)

Source: Field data 2025

Table 1 shows the tools return rate where the researcher administered 71 questionnaires and achieved to collect all administered questionnaire. On interview, the researcher succeeds to interview all four (4) heads of schools.

Demographic Information of the Respondents

Table 2: Demographic Information of the Respondents (Teachers & Heads of School)

Category	Frequency	Percentages
Sex		
Male	62	82.7
Female	13	17.3
Total	75	100
Education level		
Diploma	34	45.3
Bachelor degree	36	48
Post graduate	5	6.7
Total	75	100
Working experience		

1-5 years	34	45.3
6-10 years	28	37.3
11 and above years	13	17.3
Total		100

Source: Field Data, 2025

From Table 2, 62 (82.7%) of the teachers who took part in the current study were male, and 13 (17.3%) were female. This shows that the government did not consider gender during the time of employing in Itilima District Council, that is why more male teachers took part in the current study than female teachers. Also, among them, 34 (45.3%) had a diploma, 36 (48%) of them had a bachelor degree and 5 (7.0%) of them had master's degree. The results implies that all of the teachers who participated in this study have at least diploma in education, which is the minimal need for teaching in secondary school according to the Ministry of Education, Science and Technology. Also 34 (45.3%) teachers have been in the classroom for 1-5 years, 28 (37.3%) have been in the classroom for 6- 10 years, and 13 (17.3%) have been in the classroom for more than 11 years. This implies that majority of teachers who took part in the current study were experienced educators who offered relevant understanding on how school administration can improve students' discipline in public secondary schools.

Responsibilities of School Administrators in Enhancing Students' Discipline

Under this theme, researchers identified different responsibilities which were implemented by school administrators in enhancing the students discipline including; Invitation of guest speaker, time management, establishment of clear policies, consistence enforcement of rules, positive behaviour support program, professional development for staff, monitoring students' behaviour as well as engagement with parents and community as presented in table 2.

Table 3: Responsibilities of school administrators in enhancing students discipline N=71 (Teachers)

Aspect	Large extent Frequency (%)	Small extent Frequency (%)	Not done at all Frequency (%)
Invitation of guest speaker	23 (32.4%)	44(62.0%)	4(5.6%)
Time management	64(90.1%)	6(8.5%)	1(1.4%)
Establishment of clear policies	51(71.8%)	18(25.4%)	2(2.8%)
Consistence enforcement of rules	47(66.2%)	23(32.4%)	1(1.4%)
Positive behaviour support program	50(70.4%)	19(26.8%)	2(2.8%)
Professional development for staff	45(63.4%)	24(33.8%)	2(2.8%)
Monitoring students' behaviour	66(93.0%)	5(7.0%)	0(0%)
Engagement with parents and community	47(66.2%)	23(32.4%)	1(1.4%)

Source: Field data 2025

Invitation of Guest Speakers

On the aspect of invitations of guest speakers. Data in table 2 shows 44 (62.0%) of participants responded that invitation of guest speaker is done to the small extent, 23 (32.4%) replied to the large extent, while 4 (5.6%) respondents indicated that invitation of guest speaker is not done at all. These data imply that guest speakers are not invited frequently in schools for providing education on discipline related issues. This is evidenced by 62% of respondents who replied that it is used to the small extent. This might be happening due to the absence of funds which could be used for employing expertise for provision of counselling and guidance on the behavioural issues. Moreover, from the interview with one of the heads of schools said that "*School administrators try to invite famous people including religious leader to talk with students and advise them about discipline issues*" (interview with HoS2 in March, 2025). Another said that, "*In 2024 we invited the doctor to communicate with students on the impacts of engaging in sexual intercourse while schooling. This decreased the rate of engaging in sexual behaviours among students*" (Interview with the HoS3 in March, 2025). The interview data reveal that invitation of guest speakers helps students to be aware of the moral behaviour which impact them positively in their academic progress. The findings of the current study are in hand with the findings of Kunni (2021) which insisted educational leaders to involve neighbouring organization in discipline management of students in secondary schools this provide chance for teachers to learn on the new techniques for behaviour management. Another, Asiimwe and Kamugisha (2024) revealed that school administrators have to allocate funds which could be used for inviting special guest speaker to communicate with students on the behavioural matters. In comparison with the theory X and theory Y insists that students who belong to theory Y once they listen to guest speakers their behaviours can change positively (McGregor, 1960).

Time Management

Table 3 shows that 64 (90.1%) respondents replied that time management is done to the large extent by school administrators, 6 (8.5%) indicated that it is used to a small extent and 1(1.4%) of participants responded that it is not done at all in maintaining discipline among students. This reveals that time management is emphasized more among students which enable them to be at the right place at a right time which can prevent them from misbehaving. Moreover, from the interview with HoS4 said that *'school administration insists time management to the students including reporting early to the school and follow school academic time table'* (Interview with HoS4 in March, 2025). Another said that *"Each classroom contains a time table which guide students to be aware of their daily routines"* (Interview with HoS1 in March, 2025). Interview data implies that school administrators enhance students to follow the school time table which can prevent them from wastage of time on the issues which are not important. The findings of the current study are in line with Idris (2021) who insisted that school administrators have to manage time clearly so as to ensure that all activities are done timely in school environment. The findings have revealed the importance of having school time table in school environment. Moreover, theory X and theory Y insists that students who belongs to theory X should be closely supervised so that they can work according to the planned time table and when they violate the time table should be heavily punished (McGregor, 1960).

Establishment of Clear Policies

Table 3 shows that 51(71.8%) of participants indicated that establishment of clear policies is done to the large extent for maintaining students' discipline by school administrators, 18 (25.4%) respondents replied that it is used to a small extent, and 2 (2.8%) respondents indicated that it is not done at all. This implies that school administrators are insisting highly the students to develop their own time table which will ensure efficiency and effective on time usage. From the interview with HoS1 said that, *"School administration collaborates with teachers to ensure consistent enforcement of disciplinary measures through establishment of clear policy that will help to guide students' discipline through discipline committee and delegation of teachers into appropriate department"*. (Interview with HoS1 in March, 2025). Also, another respondent said that *"school administration ensures consistent enforcement of disciplinary measures through delegation of power to teachers in their appropriate departments"* (Interview with HoS2 in March, 2025). In addition, the HoS4 said that *"students are not allowed to go outside the school environment without uniform during the school hours. This helps them to be identified easily by the community members and bring such information to school administrators"* (Interview with HoS4). This implies that school administrators are aware on the social cultural changes which emerge in the contemporary societies and has an impact on students' behaviour which force them to enforce rules and regulations. Moreover, the theory X and theory Y insist that in the organization there must be rules and regulations which will be suitable for governing students. Teachers and school administrators should supervise students in following the rules and regulations closely and making them aware of the new established rules (McGregor, 1960).

Behaviour Support Program

Table 2 shows that 50 (70.4%) of respondents indicated that positive behaviour support program is used to a large extent in maintaining students' behaviour, while 19 (26.8%) respondents replied that it is used to a small extent and 2 (2.8%) responded that positive behaviour support program is not done at all. Statistics data shows that school administrators are aware on the importance of introducing clubs where students interact each other in enhancing students' discipline. Sometime students learn positive behaviours from their fellow students. During the interview with HoS1 said that *"In our institution teachers established positive behaviour support program including study groups, environment conservation groups which help to develop positive behaviours among the students"* (Interview with HoS1 in March, 2025). Another, HoS3 said that *"in our school, we have tendencies of visiting our neighbour school after every two months for learning how they manage students' discipline"* (Interview with HoS3 in March, 2025). The interview data implies that teachers are aware on the role of students' interaction in maintaining good discipline among students resulting to learning of good behaviours from their fellow students. The findings of the current are in line with Asimwe and Kamugisha (2024) who emphasized on the establishment behaviour support programs in school environment such as guidance and counselling programs which have positive impact on students' behaviours. To compare with theory X and Y, students who belong to theory Y when they are provided with guidance and counselling and behavioural support programs can improve their behaviours without being forced because they adopt new policies easily and put into practices (McGregor, 1960).

Consistence of Clear Policies

Table 3 shows that, above 47(66.2%) respondents also said that consistence enforcement of rules is used in large extent in maintaining students' discipline, while 23 (32.4%) respondents said that consistence enforcement of rules is used to a small extent. Also 1 (1.4%) respondent said that consistence enforcement of rules is not done at all. This reveals that secondary schools' administration in Itilima District Council consider consistence enforcement of rules to a large extent in maintaining students' discipline. Another respondent through interview also commented that, *"School administration collaborates with teachers to ensure consistent enforcement of disciplinary measures through enforcement of rules by making clear elaboration of school rules and regulations to the students by all teachers."* (Interview with HoS4 in March, 2025). This implies that school administrators foster students to follow the maintained rules and regulations which reduce misbehaviours among the students in school environment.

Professional Development of Staff

According to Table 3, 45 (63.4%) respondents agreed that professional development for staff is used to a large extent in maintaining students' discipline, while 24 (33.8%) respondents said that it is used to a small extent and 2 (2.8%) respondents said that professional development for staff is not done at all. This implies that secondary schools' administration used professional development for staff to a large extent in maintaining students' discipline. One head of school through during the interview said that interview commented that '*Our institution allows teachers to join short courses in order to develop new skills that will help them to provide good assistance to the students*' (Interview with HoS2 in March, 2025). This implies that the training which are done to teachers in working stations enhance them to develop skills which help them to manage indiscipline behaviours which are related to psychological and physical changes which occur as a result of growth.

Monitoring Students Behaviour

Table 3 shows that 66 (93.0%) respondents agreed that monitoring students' behaviour is used to a large extent and 5 (7.0%) respondents said that monitoring students' behaviour is used to a small extent. From interview guide one head of school commented that, "*School administration collaborates with teachers to ensure consistent enforcement of disciplinary measures through monitoring students' behaviour*" (Interview with HoS4 in March, 2025). The findings revealed that secondary schools' administration in Itilima District Council used monitoring students' behaviour to a large extent in maintaining students' discipline.

Engagement with Parents and Community

Table 3 shows that 47 (66.2%) respondents agreed that engagement with parents and community is used to a large extent to maintain students' behaviour, while 23 (32.4%) respondents said that it used to a small extent and 1(1.4%) respondent said that engagement with parents and community is not done at all. This implies that engagement with parents and community is done frequently for maintaining students' discipline. From the interview one head of school said that '*we involve parents and community in decision making through school board to discuss matters related to their children about discipline management and academic performance*' (Interview with HoS3 in March, 2025).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The study concludes that the behaviour management strategies which are implemented by the school administrators in school environment are effective in enhancing students' discipline since the number of students with indiscipline cases are decreasing. In addition to that, the study recommends school administrators to come up with new innovative ways for shaping students' behaviours which do not affect the students psychologically negatively. Also, school administrators have to introduce the new culture in school environment with care so as to avoid unnecessary conflict between students and management team. Another, teachers have to communicate to students frequently the principles and regulation related to discipline. Students have to follow the strictly the rules and regulations which are communicated by teachers to them so as to enhance their academic progress. The government through the ministry of education should asses the discipline management strategies which are used in school environment for ensuring students safety. Further researchers are recommended to investigate on the strategies which are used by parents at home for enhancing students' discipline.

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